

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOFIBROUS SCAFFOLDS FROM BLENDS OF GELATIN/PCL/CMC FOR HARD TISSUE ENGINEERING APPLICATION

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Abstract

Improvement of gelatin fibrous scaffold by electrospinning technique allows the preparation of ultrafine fibers with diameters ranging from micron to nanoscale fibrous materials. The electrospinning is a novel and efficient fabrication process that produced electrospun fibers through the action of an external electric field to create an electrically charged jet of polymer solution and it can able to be used as a wound closure material or tissue caused by an accident or by diseases etc. Include the development of characteristic to optimize for all applications and reduce the cost of the raw materials and develop to be used in a variety of applications. This research selected gelatin blended with polycaprolactone cellulose and carboxymethyl fabricated by using electrospinning technique for nanofibrous scaffold. We used design of experiment with voltage and feed rate for the ratios of gelatin/PCL/CMC were 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5, respectively. Gelatin and mixture was used to produce nanofiber scaffold in order to analyze fiber's physical characteristic. The gelatin solution made from dissolving gelatin in water which serves as solvent for the solution because water is a great solvent for gelatin. However, the solution used in fiber production with electrospinning, this research used organic solvent, 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol, which is also a good solvent for gelatin PCL and CMC was dissolved in water instead hence produces good raw material for fiber production using electrospinning. To characterize the scaffolds, we analyzed the physical properties by investigating the morphology and measuring the fibers size using Scanning Electron Microscope revealed that when PCL increased from 0 to 35 percent CMC set at 0 to 5 percent, fiber's size was decreased from 1.2 nm to 5.2 nm. The results revealed that the gelatin PCL/CMC (80/15/5) have an appropriate degradation rate with completely degraded after 36 h. Moreover, the gelatin/PCL/CMC (90/5/5) also showed good degradation rate. However, the gelatin (100) and gelatin/PCL/CMC (60/35/5) scaffold occurred fast degradation rate. This could simply the best condition for scaffold fabrication from biological and physical analysis which might suitable for skin tissue engineering applications.

Keywords: Scaffold, Degradation, Gelatin, Polycaprolactone, Carboxymethylcellulose, Electrospinning.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tissue engineering is an interdisciplinary field which can be referred to biomaterials development that combining scaffold, cells and biologically active molecules into functional tissues. For example porous scaffold for improving, maintaining and restoring the function of skin tissues and organs. Skin loss of patient can cause from different ways such as accidents, burns, ulcers and diseases. The scaffold, skin replacement, has been widely used and recently available. It have to be biocompatible and biodegradable material with non-toxicity. The scaffold functions have to prevent infection, accelerate

the wound healing and generate the skin tissues [1, 2]. Moreover, it can be allowed skin around the wound to reproduce a new regeneration of skin tissues in a suitable conditions. However, the presently available scaffolds are expensive due to its components. Therefore, the cheaper scaffold which has the same functions is the propose of this research. The scaffold fabrication have to be designed for supporting the recovery mechanism of skin functions. The applications of tissue engineering is the main propose of the scaffold design. Its components can be used from the naturally derived or chemically synthesized in the compositions [3, 4].

Electrospinning is a fiber production method that can produce extremely small, in the order of nanometer, fiber from synthetic polymer or natural polymer. Electrospinning uses the principle of difference in potential [5] to deliver polymer to the collector. The size of the fiber is depended on the voltage, material's flow rate, distance between the injector and the collector for fiber and concentration of the material. The result of electrospun fiber can be in the form of non-woven fiber and aligned fiber. Electrospinning is popular among various industries, including in medicine such as for production of prosthetic skin and wound dressing material [6]. When tissue loss occurs caused by burns without the body being able to rebuild it Tissue loss can be a wound caused by an accident, disease, infection or burn, when the wound reaches the dermis. Therefore, it is necessary to find skin from other areas to replace the damaged skin. Usually, the doctor takes skin from another part of the patient's body and grafts it into the wound. This is an inconvenient method and scarring the patient [7]. At present, researchers and doctors are thinking of ways to produce artificial skin or synthetic skin, and cell scaffolds [8]. Biodegradable Come to transplant the wound area. By using various types of natural polymers that are cheap and easily available, such as gelatin, collagen and chitosan [9]. in forming the structure This is for convenience and speed. And in case of wounds on the skin that have a wide area making it impossible to find other parts of skin to replace The important function of such skin substitutes is to stimulate the main cells in the dermis layer, namely fibroblast cells [10]. Around the wound growth and mobile come into structure and change shape into complete tissue [11]. Fibroblasts are the main cells in the production of collagen, which serve as the structure of the skin and keep it healthy. And create elastin [12]. To help make the skin flexible [13]. Collagen is used as a natural cell scaffold in commercially available forms. Depending on the usefulness of the application [14]. The structural strength and biodegradability depend on the bonding linkage.

The important functions of the scaffold are the appropriate degradation properties and suitable physical properties which have to be perfectly fit the rate of skin tissue regeneration that would need around 2 weeks to be completed. Moreover, their mechanical properties, ease of processing and biochemical activity are prominent in the design of tissue engineering materials that elicit a specific and desired biological response [15]. There have many researches of degradation properties of porous scaffold or fibrous scaffold. For examples the investigation of the effect of scaffold degradation rate on three-dimensional cell growth and angiogenesis. In vitro and in vivo scaffold degradation rate could be differentiated using a fast degrading polymer (e.g., poly D, L-lactic-glycolic acid co-polymer, PLGA, 50:50) and slow degrading polymer (e.g., poly caprolactone, PCL). The result found that degradation of scaffolds made of either PLGA or PCL was faster in vivo than in vitro. The more hydrophilic side chains and lower molecular weight of PLGA accelerated its degradation compared to PCL. The population with cells of scaffolds implanted in vivo was also dependent on the nature of the scaffold. The population of scaffolds with host cells, specifically with inflammatory and endothelial cells, were found to be significantly lower in the PLGA compared to the PCL scaffolds [16].

There have been studied in vitro degradation of polycaprolactone and polycaprolactone/gelatin nanofibrous scaffold. The polycaprolactone (PCL) and polycaprolactone/gelatin (PCL/Ge) 70:30 nanofibrous scaffolds were fabricated using electrospinning technique and compared on *in vitro* degradation rate to determine a more suitable scaffold for skin tissue engineering application. The result showed that both PCL and PCL/Ge (70:30) nanofibrous scaffolds were degraded after 8th week.

The degradation rate of PCL nanofibrous scaffold was slower and did not have obvious morphological changes. PCL nanofibrous scaffold with slow degradation rate was more suitable to be used for long-term implantation and long-term drug delivery carrier while PCL/Ge (70:30) nanofibrous scaffold with faster degradation rate might have the potential to be used for skin tissue engineering application [17]. The degradation behavior of hyaluronic acid-gelatin scaffolds was investigated for intestine tissue engineering. The effect of further addition of hyaluronic (HA) into the structure of the scaffolds has been evaluated in terms of microstructure and degradation behaviour of the final scaffolds. The addition of HA the degradation rate of the scaffolds became lower, and after three weeks it was a significant decrease in the mass loss of the scaffolds in PBS solution [18].

Moreover, there have been studies on the degradation of a collagen-chondroitin-6-sulfate matrix by collagenase and chondroitinase. Type I collagen-chondroitin-6-sulfate (collagen-GAG) scaffolds, produced by freeze-drying techniques. The objective was to evaluate changes in the microstructure and mechanical properties of selected collagen-GAG scaffolds as they degrade in an in vitro model system. Carbodiimide-cross-linked matrices were found to have a higher cross-link density, a higher compressive stiffness and a greater resistance to collagenase and chondroitinase, compared to non-cross-linked controls and matrices that were cross-linked by the dehydrothermal process [19]. The functional behavior of novel poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) membranes functionalized with reduced graphene oxide (rGO) nanoplatelets under simulated in vitro culture conditions (phosphate buffer solution (PBS) at 37 °C) during 1 year, in order to elucidate their applicability as scaffolds for in vitro neural regeneration. After 1 year of hydrolytic degradation, the pH was barely affected, and the rGO nanoplatelets mainly remained in the membranes which envisaged low cytotoxic effect. The degradation rate of the membranes herein reported would perfectly fit the rate of neural tissue regeneration that would need around 1 month to be completed. On the other hand, the presence of rGO nanomaterials accelerated the loss of mechanical stability of the membranes. However, it is envisioned that the gradual degradation of the PCL/rGO membranes could facilitate cells infiltration, interconnectivity, and tissue formation [20].

Gelatin is a type of protein produced by the breakdown of collagen by acids or alkalis. It looks like a light brown powder. It can be extracted from bones and skins of animals (such as cattle, buffalo, pigs). When gelatin powder is heated with water at about 32 degrees Celsius, it melts into a viscous liquid. Set aside to cool. The liquid sets to form a gel (a jelly-like appearance). Gelatin is used as a component of many products such as cosmetics, drugs, food, and photographic film. In pharmaceuticals, gelatin is used [21]. It is used in tablet coating, hard capsules and soft capsules for pharmaceutical packaging [22]. In agriculture, it is used as an intermediate for minerals needed to grow plants, etc. [23]. In food products, it has many uses.

Polycaprolactone classified as a type of thermoplastic. Classified as a polyester with a straight chain. Can be biodegradable. Currently, polycaprolactone. Much attention has been paid to the development of biodegradable plastics. But biodegradable plastics containing 45% starch mixed with polycaprolactone. still not strong enough for use Because it has a melting point of only 60 degrees Celsius and begins to soften at 40 degrees Celsius, which is a limitation in use. Use of polycaprolactone It is commonly used as an additive to resins to improve processability and improve other properties such as impact properties. Flexibility due to polycaprolactone it can be easily combined with other materials. Therefore, the use of gelatin mixed with polycaprolactone is used to produce artificial or synthetic skin [24]. Or cell cultures biodegradable

However, due to high cost of collagen this research aimed to use gelatin which is a denatured structure of collagen and has been used for medical application as a biomaterial and as an additive or gel capsules in drugs [25-26]. There have many researches approved for in vitro biocompatible test for gelatin with fibroblast cells [27-28]. The results of those research fields showed that gelatin scaffolds

could be able to maintain cells with good affinity and proliferation after 14 days of culturing without any signs of biodegradation [29].

However, gelatin has a very hydrophilic nature and relatively poor mechanical properties which limit their potential applications. An alternative polymer for blending with gelatin to improve its properties, we took an interest in using carboxymethylcellulose (CMC), a derivative of cellulose by reacted with sodium hydroxide and chloroacetic acid. It has widely used in many fields. In medical applications, due to its good viscosity building, high shear stability, biocompatibility, easily available and very cheap compared to other polysaccharides, it has widely used in many fields. CMC was used as a hydrogel for wound dressing, a scaffold for various tissue engineering applications and an injectable material for bone augmentation [16-18].

Therefore, using gelatin blended with PCL and CMC as a scaffold for skin implantation could be improved in physical and biological properties of the scaffold for skin tissue engineering. This scaffold could be used instead of collagen which is currently undergoing as skin substitute in the tissue engineering. The current study focused on the scaffolds made from gelatin blended with PCL and CMC in various ratios. Degradation and swelling properties of the gelatin/PCL/CMC scaffolds were evaluated in comparison to pure gelatin scaffold. Research Objective Study and develop skin cell scaffolds by mixing gelatin polycaprolactone and carboxymethyl cellulose for hard tissue engineering applications.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Gelatin/PCL/CMC scaffold preparation

Gelatin from Porcine Skin, 180 G Bloom, in powder form, Type B, from Fluka Analytical and 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol (TFE) (purity 99.0%) from Sigma-Aldrich were prepared. Preparation of gelatin solution was made by dissolving gelatin in TFE and stirred the solution at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. For 30 minutes at the concentration of 10 %. poly (ε-caprolactone) (PCL), with an average molecular weight of 80,000 (80 kDa) is bioresorbable and biocompatible, and has been studied as a wound dressing material since in the 1970s. Extensive research had been conducted on its biocompatibility and efficacy, both in vitro and in vivo, resulting in FDA approval of a number of medical and drug delivery devices that are composed of PCL. At present, PCL is being regarded as a soft- and hard-tissue-compatible bioresorbable material poly(ε-caprolactone) of with 2,2,2-trifluoroethanol (TFE) as the solvent. Preparation of PCL solution was made by dissolving PCL in TFE and stirred the solution at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. For 45 minutes at the concentration of 15 %.

Carboxymethylcellulose sodium salt (CMC) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA. It was medium viscosity with 400-800 cps in a 2% aqueous solution at 25 C°. The Carboxymethylcellulose sodium salt (CMC) solution was prepared by mixing powder with DI water at 0.8 wt% (w/w) then leaved it at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. for 60 minutes.

Mix Gelatin with PCL and CMC solution at temperature of 60 C°, 300 rpm. for 45 minutes. Analytical were prepared by the ratio of gelatin/PCL/CMC as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: The ratio of Gelatin/PCL/CMC.

Gelatin (%)	PCL (%)	CMC (%)	Code
100	0	0	G100P
90	5	5	G91P
80	15	5	G82P
70	25	5	G73P
60	35	5	G64P

2.2 Electrospinning technique

Gelatin/PCL/CMC solutions were prepared at the ratios of 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5 for fiber production by using electrospinning process was schematically shown in Fig. 1. The mixture was added into 5 ml syringe and the syringe was then attached to needle spinneret #20 with the hole size of 1.2 mm. The flow was controlled using syringe pump (KD-100, KD Scientific, Inc., USA) at the feed rate of 0.4 ml/h. High voltage electricity was supplied from high voltage power supply (RR501.25R/230/DDPM, Gamma High Voltage Research, USA) at 25 kV. The mixture was then injected on to collector which diameter 100 mm. 180 rpm. Was made of foil sheet. The distance between the needle's end to the foil sheet was 13 centimeters.

Fig 1: Schematic diagram of electrospinning apparatus

2.3 Dehydrothermal Treatment (DHT)

The resulted scaffold was then put into crosslinking technique by using DHT. The scaffold of gelatin PCL and CMC mixtures at the ratio of 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5 was put into desiccator with silica gel in vacuum container for 72 hours. Then the scaffold was put into vacuum oven under the temperature of 140 °C for 48 hours [30].

2.4 Gelatin/PCL/CMC Scaffold

The enzyme lysozyme was purchased from BIO BASIC INC, Canada. It was purified from chicken egg white into a lyophilized powder. It was white powder with moisture less than 6.0%. Its molecular mass was 14,307 Da and isoelectric point (pi) of 11.35. The enzyme was active over a broad pH range (6.0-9.0). This research used this enzyme for gelatin/PCL/CMC scaffold degradation. An enzyme concentration was reported in enzyme units (u) per ml. The selected concentration of enzyme was 31.2 u/ml (0.1 mg/ml PBS) [19]. The gelatin/PCL/CMC scaffold with various conditions were placed in 36-well culture plate and the enzyme solution was added with volume of 2 ml per well. Then, it was incubated in oven at 37 °C. After 0.5, 1, 1.5, 3, 9, 15, 24, 36 and 48 h, the scaffolds were removed and rinsed with DI water to remove the enzyme. Then, dried the scaffolds and weighed it. The weight remain of the scaffold after degradation was calculated by the following equation (1):

$$\text{Weight remain (\%)} = 100 - \left[\frac{W_o - W_f}{W_o} \times 100 \right] \quad (1)$$

Where: W_o is initial weight of the scaffold

W_f is final weight of the scaffold

Fig 2: Flow process chart

3. RESULTS

3.1 Surface morphology of nanofibrous scaffolds

The scaffold was analyzed its morphology by using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, EM30P-AX, COXEM(KR)) at the voltage of 15 kV with magnification power 2000x after it has been coated with gold(Gold (Au), SPT-20, COXEM(KR)) [31]. The fiber's thicknesses were also measured for at least 5 values and then calculated for the average thickness.

Fig 3: SEM images of scaffolds for nanofibers electrospinning with Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 100/0/0 (A), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 90/5/5 (B), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 80/15/5 (C), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 70/25/5 (D), Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 60/35/5 (E) and all condition were DHT for 48h.

Table 2: Fiber Diameters of Electrospun Gelatin/PCL/ CMC

Code	Range of diameter(μm)	Average diameter(μm)
G100P	3.2-3.6	3.4
G91P	1.5-1.9	1.7
G82P	1.2-2.2	1.7
G73P	2.5-3.1	2.8
G64P	2.2-5.2	3.2

Table 2 revealed that when PCL increased from 0 to 35 percent CMC set at 0 to 5 percent, fiber's size was decreased from 1.2 μm to 7.1 μm . SEM images of scaffolds for nanofibers Electrospinning with Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 100/0/0 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 3.2 μm to 3.6 μm Average diameter 3.4 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 90/5/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 1.5 μm to 1.9 μm Average diameter 1.7 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 80/15/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 1.2 μm to 2.2 μm Average diameter 1.7 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 70/25/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 2.5 μm to 3.1 μm Average diameter 2.8 μm , Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 60/35/5 size of the round fiber is Range of diameter 2.2 μm to 4.2 μm Average diameter 3.2 μm .

Fig 4: Show Graph of the resulting fiber slope from molding

Fig. 4. Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 100/0/0 Average diameter 3.4 μm it has the highest slope. Next Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 60/35/5 Average diameter 3.2 μm , Next Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 70/25/5 Average diameter 2.8 μm , Next Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 90/5/5 Average diameter 1.7 μm and Gelatin/PCL/CMC ratios of 80/15/5 Average diameter 1.7 μm respectively.

Table 3: Weight remain (%) at initial time of Gelatin/PCL/CMC

Scaffolds	Degradation time (hour)						
	0.5	1	1.5	3	24	36	48
G100P	15.20	0	0	0	0	0	0
G91P	84.22	76.11	67.31	25.22	9.64	0	0
G82P	89.11	79.22	60.11	33.12	10.11	0	0
G73P	96.53	67.54	52.11	12.66	6.08	0	0
G64P	91.22	65.33	48.12	0	0	0	0

Table 3 show at the initial time of degradation, scaffold G100P occurred the weakest in structure with weight remain of 15.20% at degradation time of 0.5 hour while scaffold G64P showed the weakest structure with weight remain of 48.12% at degradation time of 1.5 hours. The other scaffolds (G73P, G91P and G82) showed the stronger in structure with can remain their weight of 6.08%, 9.64 % and 10.11%, respectively after degraded in lysozyme for 24 hours Degradation ratio of scaffolds from electrospinning technique.

Fig 5: Degradation ratio Weight remain of scaffolds from electrospinning

Fig. 5 showed that all gelatin/PCL/CMC conditions were completely degraded after 36 hours as illustrated in figure 5. The degradation of the scaffolds which added the PCL and CMC in a condition of G91P, G82P and G73P showed the appropriate degradation rate with completely degraded after 36 hours. While, pure gelatin scaffold G100P and gelatin/PCL/CMC scaffold in a condition of G64P were completely degraded after 3 hours.

4. DISCUSSION

These results reported in this study concluded that increasing CMC into gelatin scaffolds at an appropriate content could be improved in biological and physical properties of scaffolds. The gelatin blended with PCL/CMC scaffolds at ratio of 80/15/5 (G82P) scaffold also showed good degradation rate in lysozyme solution with could remain their structure and degraded completely after 36 hours that might suitable for skin regeneration. However, the scaffold G100P and G64P showed weak in its structure with gave a low value of fast degradation rate with completely degraded after 3 hours which was not suitable for skin regeneration. These results suggested that improving gelatin scaffold by blending with PCL/CMC at the ratio of 80/15/5 and using thermal crosslinking technique might be applied for tissue engineering applications. Moreover, it could be suggested that PCL and CMC could be used as a scaffold strengthening at appropriate content. The degradation of the scaffolds would be increased if the PCL content was too much. Further research could be focused on the other treatment methods for scaffold strengthening such as the time of dehydrothermal treatment and using chemical treatments such as EDAC (1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethyl aminopropyl carbodiimide) and GTA (glutaraldehyde) which were the most commonly used for chemical crosslinking agents [30]. The other scaffold fabrication techniques such as salt-leaching technique, and 3D printing technologies of scaffolds could be compared with freeze drying technique. In addition, a higher number of samples and repetition were encouraged in order to improve experimental accuracy. The above mentions might be improved the properties of scaffold for skin tissue engineering applications.

5. CONCLUSION

Gelatin/PCL/CMC fiber produced by electrospinning technique revealed is a novel and efficient fabrication process that produced electrospun fibers through the action of an external electric field to create an electrically charged jet of polymer solution and it can able to be used as a wound closure when PCL increased from 0 to 35 percent CMC set at 0 to 5 percent, the ratios of gelatin/polycaprolactone were 100/0/0, 90/5/5, 80/15/5, 70/25/5 and 60/35/5, respectively.

Gelatin/PCL/CMC fiber produced by electrospinning technique. Scaffolds which made from gelatin blended with PCL/CMC in various conditions were studied in this research. In vitro degradation of all scaffold conditions was investigated by immersing in lysozyme in PBS solution at the desired time. The degradation results showed the best condition of gelatin/PCL/CMC ratio at 80/15/5 with completely degraded after 36 hours. However, the scaffold G100P and G64P showed the weak in their structure with completely degraded after 3 hours. It was found that too much of PCL/CMC content decreased in material strengthening. Increasing of CMC content at an appropriate content could be improved in biological and physical properties of scaffold. From all the results, it could be used this information to predict the scaffold behaviour and design an appropriate scaffold for skin tissue engineering applications.

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References

- 1) Ma P.X., and Elisseeff J. 2006. Scaffolding in Tissue Engineering, Florida, U.S.: CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, chapter 1, pp. 3-10.
- 2) Ma P.X. 2004. Scaffolds for tissue fabrication, *Materialstoday*, pp. 30-40.
- 3) Hollinger J.O. 2012. An Introduction to Biomaterials, 2nd ed., U.S.: CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, chapter 2, pp. 7-14.
- 4) Park J.B., and Bronzino J.D. 2002. Biomaterials: Principles and Applications, U.S.: CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, chapter 7, pp. 141-172.
- 5) Z.-M. Huang, Y.Z. Zhang, S.Ramakrishna, C.T. Lim. 2004. Electrospinning and mechanical characterization of gelatin nanofibers, *Polymer* 45, 5361–5368.
- 6) Y.Z. Zhang, J. Venugopal, Z.-M. Huang, C.T. Lim, S. Ramakrishna. 2006. Crosslinking of the electrospun gelatin nanofibers, *Polymer* 47, 2911–2917.
- 7) F. Wiwatwongwana, et.al. 2012. Identification of Shear Modulus of Gelatin Blended with Carboxymethylcellulose Scaffolds Using Curve Fitting Method from Compressive Test. *Journal of Materials Science Research*, 1(4): 106-113.
- 8) S. B. Lee, et.al. 2014. Study of gelatin-containing artificial skin V: fabrication of gelatin scaffolds using a salt-leaching method. *Biomaterials*, 26(14) :1969-1976.
- 9) Y. S. Cho, et.al. 2014. A novel technique for scaffold fabrication: SLUP (salt leaching using powder). *Current Applied Physics*, 14(3): 371-377.
- 10) H. J. Park, et.al. 2015. Fabrication of 3D porous silk scaffolds by particulate (salt/sucrose) leaching for bone tissue reconstruction. *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules*, 78: 215-223.
- 11) Q. Hou, et.al. 2003. Porous polymeric structures for tissue engineering prepared by a coagulation, compression molding and salt leaching technique. *Biomaterials*, 24(11): 1937-1947.
- 12) M. Alizadeh, et.al. 2013. Microstructure and characteristic properties of gelatin/chitosan scaffold prepared by a combined freeze-drying/leaching method. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*, 33(7): 3958-3967.
- 13) C. Hu, et.al. 2013. Biodegradable porous sheet-like scaffolds for soft-tissue engineering using a combined particulate leaching of salt particles and magnetic sugar particles. *Journal of Bioscience and Bioengineering*, 116(1): 126-131.
- 14) Paai Timasart. 2012. Preparation and Properties of Polymer Blend/ Bioglass® Composite for Bone Tissue Engineering Application. Master of Engineering Program in Polymer Science and Engineering Department of Materials Science and Engineering Graduate School, Silpakorn University.

- 15) Fisher J.P., Mikos A.G., and Bronzino J.D. 2007. Tissue engineering. CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group.
- 16) Sung H.J., Meredith C., Johnson C., and Galis Z.S. 2004. The effect of scaffold degradation rate on three-dimensional cell growth and angiogenesis. *Biomaterials*, vol. 25, pp. 5735-5742.
- 17) Mim L.M., and Sultana N. 2017. Comparison on in vitro degradation of polycaprolactone and polycaprolactone/gelatin nanofibrous scaffold. *Malaysian Journal of Analytical Sciences*, vol. 21, No. 3, pp. 627-632.
- 18) Shabafrooz V., Mozafari M., Mamaghani M.Y., Vashae D., and Tayebi L. Degradation behavior of hyaluronic acid–gelatin scaffolds intended for intestine tissue engineering. Oklahoma state university-Tulsa. Helmerich advanced technology research center (HATRC).
- 19) Pek Y.S., Spector M., Yannas I.V., and Gibson L.J. 2004. Degradation of a collagen-chondroitin-6-sulfate matrix by collagenase and by chondroitinase. *Biomaterials*, vol. 25, pp. 473-482.
- 20) Gonzalez S.S., Diban N., and Urtiaga A. 2018. Hydrolytic Degradation and Mechanical Stability of Poly(ϵ -caprolactone)/Reduced Graphene Oxide Membranes as Scaffolds for InViro Neural Tissue Regeneration. *Membranes*, vol. 8, No.12.
- 21) Z.M. Huang, et.al. 2004. Electrospinning and mechanical characterization of gelatin nanofibers. *Polymer*, 45(15): 5361-5368.
- 22) C.H. Huang, et.al. 2012. Evaluation of proanthocyanidin-crosslinked electrospun gelatin nanofibers for drug delivering system. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*, 32(8): 2476-2483.
- 23) J. Liang, et.al. 2016. Electrospun fibrous electrodes with tunable microstructure made of polyaniline/multi-walled carbon nanotube suspension for all-solid-state supercapacitors. *Materials Science and Engineering: B*, 211: 61-66.
- 24) M. P. Modarress, et.al. 2015. Gelatin–GAG electrospun nanofibrous scaffold for skin tissue engineering: Fabrication and modeling of process parameters. *Materials Science and Engineering: C*, 48: 704-712.
- 25) Olsen D., Yang C., Bodo M., Chang R., Leigh S., Baez J., Carmichael D., Perala M., Hamalainen E.R., Jarvinen M., and Polarek J. 2003. Recombinant collagen and gelatin for drug delivery. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews*, vol. 55, pp. 1547-1567.
- 26) Friess W. 1998. Collagen – biomaterial for drug delivery. *European Journal of Pharmaceutics and Biopharmaceutics*, vol. 45, pp. 113–136.
- 27) Tabata Y., Nagano A., Muniruzzaman Md., and Ikada Y. 1998. In vitro sorption and desorption of basic fibroblast growth factor from biodegradable hydrogels, *Biomaterials*, vol. 19, pp. 1781-1789.
- 28) Lee S.B., Jeon H.W., Lee Y.W., Lee Y.M., Song K.W., Park M.H., Nam Y.S., and Ahn H.C. 2003. Bio-artificial skin composed of gelatin and (1-3), (1-6) - ϵ -glucan, *Biomaterials*, vol. 24, pp. 2503-2511.
- 29) Lee S.B., Kim Y.H., Chong M.S., Hong S.H., and Lee Y.M. 2005. Study of gelatin-containing artificial skin V: fabrication of gelatin scaffolds using a salt-leaching method, *Biomaterials*, vol. 26, pp. 1961-1968.
- 30) Haugh M.G., Murphy C.M., McKiernan R.C., Altenbuchner C., and O'Brien F.J. 2011. Crosslinking and Mechanical Properties Significantly Influence Cell Attachment, Proliferation, and Migration within Collagen Glycosaminoglycan Scaffolds, *Tissue Engineering: Part A*.
- 31) H. Chen, J. Huang, J. Yu, S. Liu, P. Gu. 2011. Electrospun chitosan-graft-poly (ξ -caprolactone) /poly (ξ -caprolactone) cationic nanofibrous mats as potential scaffolds for skin tissue engineering, *International Journal of Biological Macromolecules* 48, 13–19
- 32) F.Wiwatwongwana, and S.Pattana. 2011. 'Influence of Blending Carboxymethylcellulose with Gelatin Scaffold on Mechanical Properties', The 2nd TSME International Conference on Mechanical Engineering (TSME-ICoME 2011), October 19-21, 2011, Sheraton Krabi Beach Resort, Krabi, Thailand. (Oral presentation)